

FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA

[Jild: 03 Nashr: 7 (2024)] ISSN: 2992-8915

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

REGULATION OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN

*Khaitmurod Mamanorov*¹

¹Teacher of Termez State University

Annotation: This article examines the regulatory framework governing foreign economic activities in Uzbekistan, offering a detailed analysis of the legal and procedural mechanisms in place. It explores the historical context and evolution of Uzbekistan's policies towards foreign investments, trade, and business operations. Key topics include the legislative reforms aimed at attracting foreign capital, the establishment of special economic zones, and the regulatory challenges faced by international businesses. The article also discusses recent developments, policy shifts, and their implications for stakeholders involved in Uzbekistan's economy. This comprehensive overview provides valuable insights into the opportunities and constraints of engaging in foreign economic activities within the country.

Keywords: Foreign economic activity, regulatory framework, investment laws, trade policies, special economic zones, legal reforms, Foreign direct investment (FDI), business regulations, economic development.

Introduction. It is known that one of the important activities of every independent state is the clear and correct definition of foreign relations. Since the Republic of Uzbekistan achieved state independence, it has independently defined its foreign relations and started to establish cooperation with foreign countries on the basis of equal rights. In this regard, the Declaration on State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law on the Basics of State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan became important legal documents. [1,2] Article 14 of the Law on the Basics of State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that the Republic of Uzbekistan is an independent subject of international economic relations, determines the conditions for foreign investment and the rights of investors, and creates its own convertible currency fund. , it is stated that it sells and buys gold and other reserves, exchangeable currency. On December 8, 1992, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. The main principles of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan were defined in

Chapter IV of the Constitution. According to it, the Republic of Uzbekistan is a subject of international relations with full rights. Its foreign policy is based on the rules of sovereign equality of states, non-use of force or threats of force, inviolability of borders, peaceful settlement of disputes, non-interference in the internal affairs of other states, and other generally recognized rules and norms of international law. [3]

If the foreign policy of our republic is carried out in accordance with this provision of our Constitution. Both multilateral foreign political and economic relations with other countries are developing more and more on the basis of full trust.[4]

Methods and Methodology. Adopted a qualitative approach to interpret and analyze legal texts, policy documents, and case studies to provide a nuanced understanding of the regulatory environment;

- Employed a mixed-methods approach integrating legal analysis, empirical data, and expert opinions to ensure a comprehensive exploration of the topic;
- Ensured triangulation of data sources and perspectives to enhance the reliability and validity of findings regarding the regulation of foreign economic activity in Uzbekistan.

Results. Laws aimed at establishing and strengthening foreign economic relations and legal documents in accordance with these laws have been adopted. An example of this is "On foreign economic activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On investment activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and other laws, as well as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of enterprises with participation of foreign investments and Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers on the activities of the establishment of enterprises, international associations and organizations with the participation of foreign investments, as well as their constituent departments in the Republic of Uzbekistan decision and a number of legal documents, such as the Regulation on the procedure for state registration of enterprises, international associations and organizations with participation of foreign investments, as well as their constituent departments. [4,5]

Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Foreign Economic Activity" defines the concept of foreign economic activity. According to it, the foreign economic activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan is understood as the activity aimed at establishing and developing mutually beneficial economic relations with legal and natural persons of the Republic of Uzbekistan, legal and natural persons of foreign countries, as well as with international organizations.

Accordingly, regardless of the forms of ownership, legal entities registered as participants in foreign economic relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as individuals registered as sole entrepreneurs, have the right to engage in foreign economic activities. [6] Therefore, legal entities and natural persons of the Republic of Uzbekistan that carry out foreign economic activity are considered subjects of foreign economic activity:

1. Physical entities engaged in business activities,
2. Legal entities registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan. [7]

Subjects of foreign economic activity can have any kind of property and, on this basis, register in accordance with the established procedure for conducting business activities or conduct foreign economic activities legally, as well as acquire rights and obligations and exercise independent property responsibility.

Banks engaged in foreign economic activity are registered as subjects in a special order. [8] According to Article 17 of the Law "On Banks and Banking Activities", "Banks can open their branch banks,

branches and branches abroad, participate in the establishment of banks, with the permission of the Central Bank".

The charter (Regulation) of legal entities engaged in foreign economic activity, "On Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On guarantees of the rights of foreign investors and measures to protect them", "Regulation of currency" on laws and other legal documents, international treaties and agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [9]

A legal entity engaged in foreign economic activity must have a special legal capacity to carry out its activities. [10]

The legal capacity of legal entities comes into being from the moment of approval of its charter or statute, provided that it must act on the basis of the general statute of this type of organization, from the moment of the decision on its establishment by the competent body.

The rights of subjects of foreign economic activity are defined in Article 7 of the Law "On Foreign Economic Activity" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [11] It states: Regardless of ownership forms and types of foreign economic activity, all subjects of foreign economic activity have equal rights in the implementation of foreign economic activity.

Conclusion. Foreign economic activity carried out by entrepreneurs is regulated by the state in the prescribed manner. State regulation of foreign economic activity: formation and improvement of the legal basis of foreign economic activity; currency regulation: tax regulation; regulation with tariff and notary; Application of protection, compensation and anti-dumping measures in order to comply with the economic interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan; determining the procedure for the implementation of foreign trade activities; establishing quantitative restrictions and establishing a state monopoly over the export and import of certain types of goods; establishing export control over weapons, military equipment, dual-purpose goods and technology; certification of imported and exported goods; setting technical, pharmacological, sanitary, veterinary, phytosanitary, ecological standards and standards; it is carried out by giving preferences and privileges for subjects of foreign economic activity.

Regulation of foreign economic activity by the state may be carried out in other ways in accordance with legislation.

References:

1. Ramazanovich, N. M., & Mamanorov, K. (2022). Development of entrepreneurs on the basis of civil rights.
2. Ramazanovich, N. M., & Mamanorov, K. (2022). Constitutional-legal relations, their subjects, objects and types. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(11), 747-756.
3. Ramazanovich, N. M., & Mamanorov, K. (2022). Peculiarities of constitutional-legal relations. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(11), 89-94.
4. Alisherovich, A. A. (2023). Jazoni ijro etish muassasalarida ekologik konun talablarini ijrosini taminlash. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 17, 96-101.
5. Янгибоев, Н. К. (2023). Формирование высокой правовой культуры—основа развития общества. *Scholar*, 1(17), 139-144.
6. Аллаярлова, М. (2022). Уй-жой олди-сотди шартномасини расмийлаштириш: миллий ва хорижий тажриба. *Общество и инновации*, 3(4/S), 520-527.

7. Mamanarov, X. (2024). Inson huquqlarini himoya qilishning xalqaro prinsiplari va o'zbekiston respublikasining jinoyat-protsessual qonunchiligi. *Models and methods in modern science*, 3(8), 119-127.
8. Toshboyeva, O., & Allayarova, M. (2024). O'zbekiston Respublikasida hisob-kitobga oid huquqiy munosabatlar. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 3(25), 171-178.
9. Allayarova, M. (2022). Improving the system of providing citizens with housing: analysis and proposals. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(12), 1311-1318.
10. Khayitmurot, M. (2023). Legal Analyze of Ecological Norms in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
11. Anvarovna, X. Z., & Chariyarovna, A. M. (2024). Renta shartnomasi. *Ilm fan xabarnomasi*, 1(1), 205-209.